

Robustness of Floquet Topological Time Crystals against Two-Level System Defects in Circuit QED

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Abstract—Discrete time crystals (DTCs) represent a nonequilibrium phase of matter [1]–[3] characterized by spontaneous breaking of discrete time-translational symmetry under periodic driving. While Floquet topological phases offer a promising route to stabilizing DTC behavior, their persistence in realistic open quantum systems remains an open problem. [4] In this work, we numerically investigate a periodically driven one-dimensional Ising chain locally coupled to a dissipative two-level system (TLS) defect, motivated by microscopic defects commonly observed in superconducting circuit-QED devices. Using Lindblad master-equation simulations implemented in QuTiP, we show that weakly dissipative TLS defects can dynamically synchronize with the Floquet edge mode and inherit its subharmonic oscillations. As the defect coupling and dissipation strength increase, the system undergoes a crossover toward decoherence and Floquet thermalization, accompanied by the suppression of edge-localized period doubling. By combining quasienergy spectroscopy, boundary-condition analysis, rigidity diagnostics, and entropy evolution, we characterize the stability limits of Floquet topological time-crystalline phases in realistic noisy quantum hardware.

Index Terms—Discrete time crystals, Floquet systems, topological edge modes, circuit QED, open quantum systems

I. INTRODUCTION

PERIODICALLY driven quantum systems provide a natural setting for realizing phases of matter without equilibrium analogues. A particular example is the discrete-time crystal (DTC), in which a system responds at an integer multiple of the driving period, thereby breaking the discrete time-translation symmetry of the drive [1], [5]. In its simplest form, a DTC exhibits a stable subharmonic response at twice the Floquet period, even when the microscopic drive is applied with period T .

Many-body localization and strong disorder provide one route to stabilizing such behavior by suppressing Floquet heating. Floquet topological phases offer a complementary route. In periodically driven one-dimensional systems, quasienergy is defined modulo $2\pi/T$, so both $\epsilon = 0$ and $\epsilon = \pi/T$ play the role of special spectral points. Edge-localized modes pinned at quasienergy π/T acquire a minus sign after every driving cycle and therefore naturally generate period-doubled dynamics. This makes Floquet topological systems a promising platform for realizing DTC-like behavior in finite quantum simulators.

The experimental motivation for this work comes

from superconducting circuit quantum electrodynamics (cQED), where arrays of transmon qubits and tunable couplers provide a flexible architecture for simulating driven spin models [6]. These devices, however, are not isolated. A common microscopic source of decoherence is the presence of two-level system (TLS) defects in dielectric materials or substrate interfaces. Such defects can exchange energy coherently with nearby qubits and subsequently relax into uncontrolled environmental modes. Recent superconducting quantum processors have shown that microscopic TLS defects can strongly limit qubit coherence times, especially near resonant frequencies. [7] Understanding how Floquet topological edge dynamics interact with such localized quantum defects is therefore important not only as a theoretical question, but also for the practical realization of robust quantum simulators.

Here we study a finite Floquet Ising chain locally coupled to a dissipative TLS defect at its boundary. The central question is whether the Floquet π -edge response survives this microscopic defect, and whether the defect simply destroys the edge dynamics or can itself become dynamically entrained by the subharmonic motion. We first identify the underlying 0 and π edge modes through quasienergy spec-

troscopy and Jordan-Wigner diagnostics. We then connect these modes to edge-enhanced magnetization dynamics, rigidity against pulse imperfections, and boundary dependence. Finally, we introduce a dissipative TLS defect through an XY exchange coupling and map the crossover between coherent synchronization and dissipative collapse [8], [9].

II. MODEL AND METHODS

A. Floquet Driven Spin Chain

We consider a one-dimensional chain of N interacting qubits modeled as spin-1/2 degrees of freedom. The system is driven periodically with period $T = T_1 + T_2$ through a two-step Floquet protocol,

$$H_{\text{sys}}(t) = \begin{cases} H_{ZZ}, & 0 \leq t < T_1, \\ H_X, & T_1 \leq t < T_1 + T_2, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where

$$H_{ZZ} = -J \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \sigma_z^{(i)} \sigma_z^{(i+1)} \quad (2)$$

is the nearest-neighbor Ising interaction and

$$H_X = -h \sum_{i=1}^N \sigma_x^{(i)} \quad (3)$$

is the transverse driving step. The corresponding one-period Floquet evolution operator is

$$U_F = \exp(-iH_X T_2) \exp(-iH_{ZZ} T_1). \quad (4)$$

The ideal spin-flip condition is $hT_2 = \pi/2$, corresponding to a nominal π rotation. Unless otherwise specified, we set $J = h = 1$ and initialize the chain in a fully polarized product state,

$$|\psi_0\rangle = \bigotimes_{i=1}^N |\uparrow\rangle_i. \quad (5)$$

B. Coupling to a Two-Level System Defect

To model a microscopic defect in a superconducting circuit, we introduce a localized TLS coupled to the edge qubit of the chain. The total Hamiltonian is

$$H_{\text{total}}(t) = H_{\text{sys}}(t) + H_{\text{defect}}, \quad (6)$$

with

$$H_{\text{defect}} = \frac{\omega_{\text{tls}}}{2} \sigma_z^{(\text{tls})} + g \left(\sigma_+^{(1)} \sigma_-^{(\text{tls})} + \sigma_-^{(1)} \sigma_+^{(\text{tls})} \right). \quad (7)$$

Equivalently, the exchange term may be written as

$$H_{\text{int}} = \frac{g}{2} \left(\sigma_x^{(\text{tls})} \sigma_x^{(1)} + \sigma_y^{(\text{tls})} \sigma_y^{(1)} \right). \quad (8)$$

Here ω_{tls} is the TLS splitting and g is the local exchange coupling between the defect and the boundary qubit. This form captures the energy-exchange character of a resonant microscopic defect coupled to a superconducting qubit.

C. Open Quantum System Dynamics

Dissipation of the TLS into uncontrolled environmental degrees of freedom is described using a Lindblad master equation,

$$\dot{\rho} = -i[H_{\text{total}}(t), \rho] + \gamma \mathcal{D}[\sigma_-^{(\text{tls})}] \rho, \quad (9)$$

where

$$\mathcal{D}[L] \rho = L \rho L^\dagger - \frac{1}{2} \{L^\dagger L, \rho\}. \quad (10)$$

The parameter γ denotes the spontaneous emission rate of the TLS defect. Exact finite-size open-system simulations are performed using the Quantum Toolbox in Python (QuTiP).

D. Numerical Simulation Parameters

Unless otherwise specified, numerical simulations were performed for a Floquet spin chain containing $N = 6$ qubits coupled to a single ancillary TLS defect, giving a total Hilbert space dimension of $N_{\text{total}} = 7$ qubits. The Ising interaction strength and transverse driving field were fixed at $J = h = 1$ throughout the simulations.

The Floquet protocol consisted of two sequential driving steps with durations

$$T_1 = 0.85 \left(\frac{\pi}{4} \right), \quad T_2 = 0.95 \left(\frac{\pi}{2} \right),$$

corresponding respectively to the interaction and transverse-field segments of the drive cycle. The TLS defect was coupled to the left boundary qubit through an XY exchange interaction with coupling strength g_{defect} , while dissipation of the TLS into the environment was modeled using a Lindblad decay rate γ_{TLS} . The slight detuning away from the ideal π -pulse condition was intentionally introduced in order to probe the robustness of the subharmonic response against drive imperfections.

Unless otherwise noted, representative simulations were performed with

$$g_{\text{defect}} = 0.5, \quad \gamma_{\text{TLS}} = 0.01,$$

over approximately 40 Floquet periods. Parameter scans over both g_{defect} and γ_{TLS} were used to construct the dynamical phase diagrams shown in later sections.

The parameter regime considered here is compatible with experimentally accessible superconducting circuit-QED platforms, where microscopic TLS defects typically exhibit coherent coupling strengths in the 10–100 MHz range and dissipation rates on the order of MHz.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Floquet Topological Edge Modes

We first identify the microscopic origin of the period-doubled edge dynamics by analyzing the Floquet quasienergy spectrum. Using the Jordan-Wigner mapping, the driven spin chain can be represented as an effective free-fermion system, allowing the Floquet eigenmodes and their spatial profiles to be directly visualized. [10], [11].

Fig. 1. **Floquet quasienergy spectrum and edge localization.** The quasienergies ϵT are plotted as a function of the transverse drive parameter T_2 . The color map represents the edge localization weight $W_\alpha = |\psi_1|^2 + |\psi_N|^2$. Bright branches pinned at $\epsilon = 0$ and $\epsilon = \pm\pi$ correspond to Majorana zero modes and Floquet π -modes localized at the system boundaries.

As shown in Fig. 1, strongly localized edge states appear at the special quasienergies $\epsilon = 0$ and $\epsilon = \pm\pi$. In a static topological system, protected boundary modes occur at zero energy. Floquet periodicity

introduces an additional protected quasienergy gap at $\epsilon = \pi/T$, allowing boundary modes whose Floquet eigenvalue is -1 . These π modes acquire a minus sign after each driving cycle. As a result, observables constructed from superpositions of 0 and π modes naturally exhibit a doubled oscillation period of $2T$.

Fig. 2. **Spatiotemporal evolution of Floquet edge modes.** (Left) Isolated Majorana zero mode exhibiting static edge localization. (Middle) Isolated Floquet π -mode showing robust $2T$ sign reversal. (Right) Coexistence phase containing both zero and π modes, producing a beating structure localized at the boundaries.

The corresponding real-time mode evolution is shown in Fig. 2. The zero mode remains static at the boundary, while the Floquet π -mode alternates sign after every driving cycle. In the coexistence regime, interference between the two topological sectors produces a beating pattern confined to the edges. These free-fermion diagnostics provide the eigenstate-level explanation for the interacting spin dynamics studied below.

Fig. 3. **Edge versus bulk Floquet dynamics.** The edge qubit exhibits robust period-doubled oscillations, while the bulk response dephases within the first several driving periods due to interaction-induced scrambling.

B. Edge-Localized Time-Crystalline Dynamics

We next simulate the interacting spin dynamics directly in the periodically driven Ising chain.

Figure 3 shows that the edge spin undergoes stable stroboscopic oscillations between $+1$ and -1 , corresponding to a subharmonic response at $\nu = 1/2$. By contrast, the bulk signal dephases within roughly ten driving periods and displays a strongly reduced coherent amplitude. This spatial distinction is consistent with the localization of the Floquet π mode near the system boundary.

C. Robustness Against Initial-State Preparation

A possible concern is that the observed period doubling could be an artifact of the fully polarized initial state. To test this, we compare the dynamics for several initial configurations.

Fig. 4. **Robustness against initial-state preparation.** Time evolution of the edge and bulk magnetization for three distinct initial states: fully polarized, random many-body, and alternating product states. Across all cases, the edge spin maintains stable period-doubled oscillations.

As shown in Fig. 4, the edge-localized subharmonic oscillations persist for fully polarized, random, and alternating product initial states. The reduced oscillation amplitude for random initial states originates from destructive interference among many Floquet eigenmodes with unrelated phases. Nevertheless, the dominant $2T$ structure remains visible, indicating that the observed response is not tied to a specially engineered product state.

D. Floquet Rigidity Plateau

We next ask whether the response is stable against imperfect control pulses. This test is important because a purely trivial spin-flip protocol would be expected to lose frequency locking once the drive is detuned away from the ideal π -pulse condition.

Figure 5 shows that the period-doubled response survives over a substantial region of drive parameter space. The response is not confined to the ideal point $hT_2/\pi = 0.5$. Instead, it remains locked

Fig. 5. **Floquet rigidity plateau under pulse imperfections.** The normalized subharmonic spectral response at frequency $\nu = 1/2$ is mapped as a function of the Ising interaction strength JT_1/π and transverse rotation angle hT_2/π . The white marker denotes the ideal drive point. Rather than appearing only at a fine-tuned parameter point, the subharmonic response persists over a broad finite region, forming a rigidity plateau characteristic of Floquet time-crystalline dynamics.

to $\nu = 1/2$ over a finite pulse-error window. In contrast, a trivial near- π spin-flip protocol without stabilizing interactions would be expected to lose synchronization rapidly once the pulse error exceeds a small threshold. The observed rigidity plateau therefore provides evidence for a stable Floquet subharmonic regime rather than a fine-tuned control artifact.

E. Boundary Dependence of the Subharmonic Response

To verify the boundary origin of the enhanced subharmonic response, we compare open and periodic boundary conditions.

Fig. 6. **Boundary dependence of the subharmonic response.** Under Open Boundary Conditions (OBC), the edge site exhibits a strongly enhanced subharmonic spectral peak at $\nu = 1/2$. Under Periodic Boundary Conditions (PBC), where the physical boundary is removed, the edge and bulk responses become identical.

As shown in Fig. 6, the enhanced subharmonic response disappears once the physical boundary is

removed. Under periodic boundary conditions, all sites become equivalent, and the edge/bulk distinction vanishes. This comparison shows that the dominant subharmonic oscillation under open boundary conditions is tied to boundary-localized Floquet modes rather than to a spatially uniform global rotation. [9], [12]

F. TLS-Induced Synchronization and Topological Collapse

After establishing the closed-system Floquet response, we introduce a localized TLS defect coupled to the edge qubit. The defect is not directly driven by the Floquet protocol, but it exchanges excitations with the edge through the XY interaction in Eq. (8) and relaxes at rate γ .

To characterize the interaction between the boundary Floquet mode and the ancillary TLS defect, we define synchronization as the emergence of a stable subharmonic Fourier peak at $\nu = 1/2$ in the TLS response together with phase locking to the edge oscillation.

Fig. 7. **Floquet-induced synchronization of a microscopic TLS defect.** The edge qubit (red) exhibits robust period-doubled oscillations. Although the TLS defect (blue) is not directly driven, it gradually synchronizes with the edge mode through the XY exchange interaction.

Figure 7 shows a representative weakly dissipative case. The edge qubit maintains its period-doubled response, while the TLS gradually develops oscillations at the same subharmonic frequency. This behavior can be interpreted as a form of dynamical synchronization between the localized defect and the topological edge mode. The synchronization onset occurs after several Floquet cycles, indicating a competition between coherent edge-mode pumping and dissipative relaxation of the TLS defect.

Fig. 8. **Dynamical phase diagram of TLS-induced topological collapse.** The late-time edge oscillation amplitude is plotted as a function of TLS coupling strength g and dissipation rate γ . Weak coupling and weak dissipation preserve the Floquet edge response, whereas strong coupling combined with strong dissipation drives rapid decoherence and suppresses the subharmonic oscillations.

To characterize the stability of the synchronized regime, we scan the (g, γ) parameter space in Fig. 8. For weak coupling or weak dissipation, the edge response remains coherent. In the opposite limit, the TLS behaves as a localized lossy channel that absorbs coherence from the Floquet edge mode and quenches the subharmonic oscillations. The crossover boundary roughly follows the competition between coherent exchange and dissipative loss: once the exchange coupling becomes comparable to or smaller than the TLS decay rate, information transferred into the defect is rapidly lost to the bath. The crossover approximately occurs when the coherent exchange scale g becomes comparable to the dissipative loss rate γ , marking the transition between synchronized edge-TLS dynamics and irreversible decoherence.

G. Entropy Signatures of Floquet Thermalization

To quantify the crossover between coherent synchronization and dissipative collapse, we compute the subsystem von Neumann entropy,

$$S_{vN}(\rho_{\text{sub}}) = -\text{Tr}(\rho_{\text{sub}} \ln \rho_{\text{sub}}). \quad (11)$$

In the Lindblad setting, this quantity captures both entanglement with the remaining spins and mixedness induced by the environment.

Figure 9 reveals two distinct regimes. In the strongly dissipative phase, the entropy rapidly grows

Fig. 9. **Subsystem von Neumann entropy dynamics.** In the strongly dissipative regime (gray dashed line), the entropy rapidly increases and saturates at a finite plateau, signaling Floquet thermalization and the destruction of coherent edge dynamics. Inset: in the weakly dissipative regime, the entropy remains vanishingly small ($S_{v,N} \sim 10^{-8}$), demonstrating that the synchronized edge-TLS subsystem preserves a weakly entangled nonequilibrium state.

and saturates near a finite plateau, indicating decoherence and Floquet thermalization. By contrast, in the weakly dissipative synchronized regime the entropy remains extremely small throughout the evolution. The edge-TLS subsystem therefore avoids significant thermalization and remains close to a coherent nonequilibrium state, even in the presence of a microscopic defect.

Together, these results show that Floquet topological edge dynamics can remain stable against weakly dissipative localized TLS defects, while also identifying the parameter regime in which strong defect coupling and dissipation destroy the subharmonic response.

IV. CONCLUSION

In summary, we investigated the robustness of Floquet topological time-crystalline dynamics in the presence of localized dissipative TLS defects motivated by realistic circuit-QED hardware. By combining Floquet quasienergy analysis with exact Lindblad simulations, we demonstrated that boundary-localized π modes generate stable subharmonic oscillations that remain robust against pulse imperfections, initial-state variations, and moderate environmental coupling.

Most notably, we identified a synchronization regime in which a weakly dissipative TLS defect dynamically inherits the period-doubled oscillations of the Floquet edge mode. As the defect coupling and dissipation strength increase, the system crosses over into a thermalized regime characterized by entropy growth and suppression of the edge response.

These results suggest that Floquet topological phases can retain significant robustness even in the presence of realistic microscopic defects commonly observed in superconducting quantum devices. More broadly, the present work highlights the interplay between topology, nonequilibrium dynamics, and open-system decoherence in driven quantum simulators.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Numerical simulations were implemented in Python using QuTiP. Simulation scripts and additional numerical details are available from the author upon request.

The author thanks the instructors and teaching staff of the UC Berkeley quantum and nonlinear optics course for valuable discussions and guidance.

Codings can be checked through link : https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1k7ZDSTd_cC15EuAdMmsNZNt5OfrtEWjf?usp=sharing and https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1BoAmFHy8aQ_nqWzyVNice1xSq5a9u4bY?usp=sharing

REFERENCES

- [1] V. Khemani, A. Lazarides, R. Moessner, and S. L. Sondhi, “Phase structure of driven quantum systems,” *Physical Review Letters*, vol. 116, no. 25, p. 250401, 2016.
- [2] D. V. Else, B. Bauer, and C. Nayak, “Floquet time crystals,” *Physical Review Letters*, vol. 117, no. 9, p. 090402, 2016.
- [3] N. Y. Yao, A. C. Potter, I.-D. Potirniche, and A. Vishwanath, “Discrete time crystals: Rigidity, criticality, and realizations,” *Physical Review Letters*, vol. 118, no. 3, p. 030401, 2017.
- [4] H.-P. Breuer and F. Petruccione, *The Theory of Open Quantum Systems*. Oxford University Press, 2002.
- [5] X. Mi *et al.*, “Time-crystalline eigenstate order on a quantum processor,” *Nature*, vol. 601, pp. 531–536, 2022.
- [6] B. Wang, J. Quan, J. Han, X. Shen, H. Wu, and Y. Pan, “Observation of photonic topological floquet time crystals,” *Laser & Photonics Reviews*, vol. 16, no. 5, p. 2100469, 2022.
- [7] J. M. M. *et al.*, “Decoherence in josephson qubits from dielectric loss,” *Physical Review Letters*, vol. 95, no. 21, p. 210503, 2005.
- [8] T. Kitagawa, E. Berg, M. Rudner, and E. Demler, “Topological characterization of periodically driven quantum systems,” *Physical Review B*, vol. 82, no. 23, p. 235114, 2010.
- [9] M. S. Rudner, N. H. Lindner, E. Berg, and M. Levin, “Anomalous edge states and the bulk-edge correspondence for periodically driven two-dimensional systems,” *Physical Review X*, vol. 3, no. 3, p. 031005, 2013.
- [10] L. Jiang, T. Kitagawa, J. Alicea, A. Akhmerov, D. Pekker, G. Refael, J. I. Cirac, E. Demler, M. Lukin, and P. Zoller, “Majorana fermions in equilibrium and in driven cold-atom quantum wires,” *Physical Review Letters*, vol. 106, no. 22, p. 220402, 2011.

- [11] M. Thakurathi, A. Patel, D. Sen, and A. Dutta, “Floquet generation of majorana end modes and topological invariants,” *Physical Review B*, vol. 88, no. 15, p. 155133, 2013.
- [12] Y. Pan and B. Wang, “Time-crystalline phases and period-doubling oscillations in one-dimensional floquet topological insulators,” *Physical Review Research*, vol. 2, no. 4, p. 043239, 2020.